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Online Shopping System

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Abstract

Online Shopping system is a method to buy or purchase any material electronically. This is a method by which we can buy any kind of item easily from a various online sites like amazon, flipkart and many more. By this paper we are discussing about the project entitle "Online Shopping System". Basically this paper describe about how we can buy an electronic items in online manner. All the modules of this paper describe for the online shopping system of electronic products.

Keywords: Online shopping, Electronic Item.

1. Introduction

With the rapidly evolving nature of technology, various experiences have shifted either partially or completely to the digital world, including the shopping experience and the service delivery experience[1]. Indeed, as the Internet has become a major channel of product and service delivery, and as a new generation

of 'digital natives' has become a key target for major retailers, the online shopping experience has taken on vital importance. In fact, experience is considered "the key battleground for today's global competition[1]. As by the project we are simplifying the complication of an Organization. The project mainly deals with the Users & Admin. Job Record handling, user (employee) complaint are also maintained by that . The present software is named as "Online Shopping", future version of the project will include several other user friendly features. This project report prepared by our self by keeping in view in need for efficient, less time consuming and safe .we have put our heart and soul in making this project successfully but if there are any faults or suggestion , they are most welcome. The present study aims to examine purchase behavior in personalized online shopping by employing complexity theory, based on customers' online shopping experience and online shopping motivations[2]. With the development of the internet, customers are able to purchase medical equipment not only at the pharmacy but through the internet; notwithstanding, the studies for analyzing the effects of purchasing intention on acquiring medical equipment are deficient[3]. Because of online shopping system the shopping method is become more transparent from the older system.

Fig: Online Shopping System

1.1 Objective

The objective of this paper to introduce about the main aim of the project that is to

maintain all the information in a systematic and accurate way. All of the module of the project have been made with these objectives in mind:-

- Electronic shop management system is developed specifically to ease the needs of the Department of sales and purchase.
- This system will reduce the manual operation required to maintain all the records of sales and purchase.
- This system allows to search number of stocks details of electronic items with appropriate company.
- This application shall also have some features like profit loss reports displaying in the same window.
- It will be having user friendly GUIs that will guide the user to easily achieve the same.
- In addition to this the application also supports feature to generate different kinds of reports.
- The application is to be fully developed online shopping project using php, Hence its main intension to computerize the electronic shop.

1.2 Literature Review

In February 2017 Fatema Kawaf a, Stephen Tagg, say that, the research aims to explore the essence of the online shopping experience as constructed by online users, using their own words and constructions[1]. Online shopping is method by which we can save our time of walking markets and dealing with merchant, we just need to choose from online site there we have a lots of option. In October 2016, Pappas IO, Kourouthanassis PE, Giannakos MN, Lekakos G. deals that, The present study aims to examine purchase behavior in personalized online shopping by employing complexity theory, based on customers' online shopping experience and online shopping motivations[2]. We know that all the online shopping system makes the transparency about the product and their manufacturing items. Somehow we also know

that we also have fake online companies that make as fool by delivery fault or wrong products but we have a consumer forum their we can complain for such a company and their products. This online shopping systems generates the business e-business. In July 2016 Hong-Oanh Nguyen n says that, the adoption of e-business has allowed transport and logistics service providers to assume a new role in the supply chain as intermediaries or online e-market places[4]. All the literature review tell us that the online system makes easy for shopping to us.

1.3 Problems in Existing System

In the existing system the transactions are done only manually but in proposed system we have to computerize all the banking transaction using the software Staff Management System.

- Lack of security of data.
- More man power.
- Time consuming.
- Consumes large volume of pare work.
- Needs manual calculations.

1.3 Proposed System

The proposed system has technical capacity of required to hold the data. This project is efficient and responds quickly for various enquires regardless of number of locations. The system proposed could be expanded easily and efficiency, whenever required.

1.4.1 Snap Shot of a Project

Fig: Login Form

Fig: Home Page

Fig.: Contact Detail From

Fig: DFD of an Online Shopping System

Fig: ER of a Shopping System

2. Methodology

2.1 PHP

PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor (or simply PHP) is a server-side scripting language designed for web development but also used as a general-purpose programming language. It was originally created by Rasmus Lerdorf in 1994,[3] the PHP reference implementation is now produced by The PHP Group.[4] PHP originally stood for Personal Home Page,[3] but it now stands for the recursive acronym PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor.

Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/PHP>

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
```

```
<html>
```

```
<body>
```

```
<?php
```

```
echo "My first PHP script!";
```

```
?>
```

```
</body>
```

```
</html>
```

Source: <https://www.w3schools.com/php/default.asp>

2.2 Microsoft SQL Server 2005

Microsoft SQL Server 2005 Express Edition has been designed with older Microsoft operating systems in mind. Offering bespoke data management options as well as the ability to enhance levels of performance, this bundle can be downloaded in the event that the original SQL copy was lost or otherwise corrupted. This is the official software package offered by Microsoft. Originally published in 2005, Microsoft SQL Server 2005 Express Edition provides the user with all of the most important tools to better manage his or her system. As the name may already suggest, this bundle can be used with older versions of Microsoft such as Microsoft XP and Microsoft 2000. Some core processes include advanced data protection, the better management of online applications and superior data storage solutions. This software can come in quite handy if a system seems to be running poorly.

Source:

<https://microsoft-sql-server-2005-express-edition.en.softonic.com/#app-softonic-review>

2.3 HTML

HTML (Hypertext Markup Language) is the set of markup symbols or codes inserted in a file intended for display on a World Wide Web browser page. The markup tells the Web browser how to display a Web page's words and images for the user. Each individual markup code is referred to as an element (but many people also refer to it as a tag). Some elements come in pairs that indicate when some display effect is to begin and when it is to end.

Source: <https://searchmicroservices.techtarget.com>

2.4 CSS

CSS stands for "Cascading Style Sheet." Cascading style sheets are used to format the layout of Web pages. They can be used to define text styles, table sizes, and other aspects of Web pages that previously could only be defined in a page's HTML.

CSS helps Web developers create a uniform look across several pages of a Web site. Instead of defining the style of each table and each block of text within a page's HTML, commonly used styles need to be defined only once in a CSS document.

Source: <https://techterms.com/definition/css>

2.5 Feasibility Study

A feasibility study is an analysis of how successfully a project can be completed, accounting for factors that affect it such as economic, technological, legal and scheduling factors. Project managers use feasibility studies to determine potential positive and negative outcomes of a project before investing a considerable amount of time and money into it.

Source: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/f/feasibility-study.asp>

3. Result

The project is discussion is an attempt to attain all the above Said objective. Its development was man to replace the manual system and Toachieve the goal to maximum accuracy and most efficiently. But like every other system might process fault to its credits and has its own limitations.

4. Conclusion

Now a days computerizations of existing manual system is going on a large Scale because of versality, Speed, Accuracy and Diligence it offer to its users. Computer provide practical means to organize thing systematically and economically in the organization the use of computer for maging transactions, informations processing and preparation of reports can prove To be a blessing.

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